

Taico

Teacher-AI Complementarity

TAICO EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Project Number: 101177268

D2.2 – TAICO EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

Project / Action Title	TAICo- Teacher-AI Complementarity
Project / Action Acronym	TAICo
Project Reference No. / Action No.	101177268
Work Package No.	2
Deliverable	2.2
Deliverable Version	1.6
Date	30.04.2026
Responsible Partner	UOULU
Contributing Partners	TLU, UWK, RU, RUB, UCL
Authors	Justin Edwards (UOULU), Ekaterina Astafeva (UOULU), Kairit Tammets (TLU), Tobias Ley (UWK), Anne-Wil Kramer (RU), Ann-Christine Fahls (RUB), Florian Gnadlinger (UWK), Wannapon Suraworachet (UCL), Qi Zhou (UCL)
Reviewers	Gerti Pishtari (UWK)
Dissemination Level/Access	Public
License	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License

History of Changes / Versions

Version/Revision	Date	Author	Description (of Changes)
0.1	10.02.2026	Justin Edwards	Initial outline
0.2	16.03.2026	Ekaterina Astafeva	Initial content
0.3	07.04.2026	Justin Edwards & Ekaterina Astafeva	Sharable outline for partners
0.4	08.04.2026	Kairit Tammets & Tobias Ley	Revised outline for partners
0.5	08.04.2026	Ekaterina Astafeva & Justin Edwards	Internal edits
0.6	13.04.2026	Kairit Tammets & Tobias Ley	Initial draft with TAICo concept content
1.0	21.04.2026	Anne-Wil Kramer, Ann-Christine Fahls, Kairit Tammets, Florian Gnadlinger, Wannapon Suraworachet, Qi Zhou,	Partner content additions
1.1	23.04.2026	Ekaterina Astafeva	Edits and summary of partner content
1.2	24.04.2026	Kairit Tammets & Tobias Ley	Argumentation and style alignment
1.3	25.04.2026	Justin Edwards, Ekaterina Astafeva	Comprehensive edit for internal reviewer
1.4	27.04.2026	Gerti Pishtari	Internal review
1.5	28.04.2026	Ekaterina Astafeva	Post internal review edits
1.6	29.04.2026	Tobias Ley	Post internal review argumentation revision

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

<i>Executive summary</i>	4
<i>1. Introduction</i>	5
1.1. Scope within the TAICo project.....	6
<i>2. Conceptual foundations of the TAICo evaluation framework</i>	7
2.1 Co-design as the entry point of the framework.....	8
2.2 Layer 1: Complementarity conditions.....	8
2.3 Layer 2: Complementarity enacted.....	9
2.4 Layer 3: Complementarity effects.....	10
<i>3. Research Focus of the Project</i>	11
3.1 The Effects of AI on teaching tasks, skills and knowledge (WP1).....	11
3.2 The role of AI tool design on complementarity (WP3).....	11
3.3 Evaluating professional learning and support for teacher-AI complementarity (WP4)	12
<i>4. Units of analysis, research methods and instruments</i>	13
4.1 Unit of analysis	13
4.2 Sources of evidence.....	14
4.3 Capturing main constructs across multiple sources of evidence.....	15
Task level changes.....	15
Skill level changes	16
Complementarity configuration	16
Task Performance.....	17
Workload	17
Trust.....	19
Readiness for adoption	20
<i>5 Case-level Research for Phase II</i>	21
5.1 The planned studies for Phase II of the project	21
5.2 Research plans for Phase II of the project	22
5.3 Ethics, gender, and equality considerations.....	25
<i>6. Conclusions and future outlook: evaluation of TAICo results to form a Knowledge Base</i>	26
<i>7. References</i>	27

Executive summary

Deliverable 2.2 (D2.2) of the TAIco (Teacher-AI Complementarity) project forms part of Work Package 2 (WP2), which focuses on the coordination of empirical studies across the six TAIco Cases, each of which exploring a way to integrate the use of advanced AI tools into authentic educational tasks and settings and studying the emerging complementarity between the teachers' skills and the AI's capabilities. This deliverable establishes a shared evaluation framework for the confirmatory research phase of TAIco (Phase II), providing the methodological structure through which teacher-AI complementarity is analysed, compared, and synthesised across the diverse TAIco cases of the project.

D2.2 comprises two main tasks. The first task involves the development of the TAIco Evaluation Framework, which translates the framework of teacher-AI complementarity introduced in D1.1 into a process-oriented structure for evaluating how complementarity is shaped, enacted, and what effects it produces on teachers' work and professional development. The framework is organised around three interconnected layers- complementarity conditions, complementarity enacted, and complementarity effects- and integrates analytical approaches from WP1, WP3, and WP4 to capture teacher-AI complementarity from both a human-computer interaction and a professional practice perspective. The framework recognises that teacher-AI complementarity takes different forms depending on the pedagogical task, the design of the AI system, the teacher's professional background, and the institutional context, and is therefore designed to capture variation rather than prescribe a single model of complementarity.

The framework further specifies the key constructs to be evaluated across the TAIco cases (including task-level and skill-level changes, complementarity configurations, teacher agency, cognitive load, trust, pedagogical meaningfulness, professional knowledge, and readiness for adoption), the units of analysis, and the sources of evidence through which these constructs can be captured in a comparable way across the project. The second task involves the coordination of case-level research plans for Phase II, in which each TAIco partner outlines their planned field studies and design implementation and evaluation studies, including their research questions, designs, methods, and ethical considerations.

This deliverable is structured into six sections. Section 1 provides an overview of D2.2 and its scope within the TAIco project. Section 2 presents the conceptual foundations of the evaluation framework, including its three-layer evaluation logic and the role of co-design as the entry point of the framework. Section 3 describes the research focus of each contributing work package and the overarching research questions guiding their contributions to the evaluation. Section 4 specifies the units of analysis, sources of evidence, and the key constructs to be captured across the TAIco cases. Section 5 presents the case-level research plans for Phase II, including research questions, designs, methods, and ethics and equality considerations for each TAIco partner. Finally, Section 6 outlines the future outlook for how the evaluation framework will support the delivery of the TAIco Knowledge Base, a project-level result synthesising the empirical findings of the project.

1. Introduction

The TAICo evaluation framework is developed to provide a shared methodological guidance for analysing, comparing, and progressively refining the notion of Teacher-AI Complementarity as introduced in [D1.1](#) across empirical and design-oriented studies of the project. While the TAICo model aims to explain how teachers and AI can work together in educational settings/contexts in ways that are pedagogy-grounded and developmentally valuable, this requires a common evaluation framework that can capture how complementarity is designed, how it is enacted in practice and what kinds of effects it produces for teachers' work and professional development.

Across the WPs of the project, teacher-AI complementarity is approached from different, but interconnected perspectives. WP1 focuses on conceptualising and validating complementarity as a theoretical and methodological construct; WP3 investigates the design, affordances and interaction features of teacher-facing AI systems; and WP4 investigates how professional learning, co-design, and classroom implementation shape teachers' ability to work productively with AI. TAICo's shared evaluation framework serves as the integrative backbone that connects the WPs through shared constructs and a common unit of analysis.

Within TAICo, the framework serves three closely connected functions. **First**, it provides **a common language** to produce evidence across the TAICo cases. Teacher-AI complementarity may take different forms depending on the pedagogical task, the design of the AI tool, the teacher's prior competence, the training and support provided, and the institutional context. Therefore, the framework enables the documentation and comparison of different patterns of task distribution, teacher agency and professional consequences across observation studies, co-design activities, field studies, and professional learning interventions. **Second**, the framework is **a basis for model refinement**, which is intentionally developed iteratively. The framework will impact the cyclical refinement of the TAICo model. While the model itself derives from our empirical activities – i.e., the observation studies ([D2.1](#)) informed the first version, while the evaluations will further help to refine it – these research activities are operationalised through the TAICo evaluation framework. **Third**, the framework focuses the project on critical dimensions of teacher-AI complementarity, and what impact they have on the long run. It goes beyond short-term gains and focuses on teacher professionalism, whether teachers retain or strengthen pedagogical judgement, and whether AI supports professional agency.

The TAICo evaluation framework is designed to explain under what conditions teacher-AI complementarity emerges, how it is enacted and what kinds of professional and pedagogical effects it produces. To address this question, the framework conceptualises teacher-AI complementarity as a process, which unfolds from co-design that establishes the conditions for complementarity, through its enactment to the effects. Within this process, the framework differentiates immediate changes in teacher work and broader developmental and professional consequences.

Further, the TAICo evaluation framework is based on the initial conceptual framework of Teacher-AI complementarity proposed in [D1.1](#), which identifies teacher-AI complementarity as a situated interaction around pedagogical tasks, shaped by the interplay between teacher characteristics, AI features, AI affordances, AI system characteristics and wider deployment conditions, serving as the conceptual foundation for the evaluation framework (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 TAIco Framework

D1.1, Initial Framework of Teacher-AI Complementarity, defines the project’s analytical focus at the level of pedagogical tasks, subtasks, actions, skills, and interaction configurations, rather than treating complementarity as a general property of a tool or a job. This makes complementarity a phenomenon that must be examined through teacher professional practice and observable teacher–AI interaction in authentic educational settings.

D2.2 has several closely connected tasks. First, it defines the key constructs to be evaluated across the cases, so that the project has a common articulation of prerequisites, dimensions, and impacts of teacher–AI complementarity. Second, it describes how partners plan their execution and evaluation of Phase II studies systematically across different cases, contexts, and study designs. Third, it explains how the evidence generated through the cases will be used to refine the complementarity model and to inform the development of AI design guidelines and professional learning strategies. Fourth, it ensures that methods planned for Phase II studies consider ethics, gender, intersectionality, and equality as integral dimensions of TAIco through the coordination of human research ethics review practices and the consideration of teacher identity characteristics within the evaluation framework.

1.1. Scope within the TAIco project

D2.2 builds on the work already completed in TAIco, especially [D2.1 Observational studies coordination report](#), [D1.1 Initial Model of Teacher-AI Complementarity](#), [D3.1 Ethical AI Taxonomy and Initial guidelines for Teacher-AI Complementarity](#), and [D4.1 Training Framework for AI Implementation in Professional Settings](#).

D2.2 draws on [D1.1](#), the Initial Model of Teacher-AI Complementarity, to establish the conceptual and analytical basis for evaluating task-level change, skill and knowledge change, and complementarity configurations across the TAIco cases. [D1.1](#) defines complementarity as a configuration that becomes observable when pedagogical tasks are analysed at sufficient granularity and when the distribution of actions, skills, and knowledge between teachers and AI can be traced systematically. It further introduces the methodological components that support this analysis, including task analysis, skill and knowledge analysis, and complementarity analysis. Through this lens, **the evaluation framework considers the results of TAIco through the perspective of the changes to teaching** at these granularities.

D2.2 uses [D3.1](#), the Ethical AI Taxonomy and Initial guidelines for Teacher-AI Complementarity, to incorporate the AI taxonomy into the evaluation of project-level results. [D3.1](#) proposes a taxonomy that defines the constructs and design features of AI Ed systems which influence the effectiveness, efficacy, and ethical dimensions of teacher–AI complementarity. As such, **the evaluation framework considers TAIco results through the perspective of human-computer interaction** with attention to the characteristics of the teachers and the AI system, which [D3.1](#) identifies as influential on this interaction.

D2.2 likewise builds on D4.1, 1 the Training Framework for AI Implementation in Professional Settings, to include the training framework into the evaluation of project-level results. D4.1 conceptualises how AI affordances interact with teachers’ professional knowledge, beliefs, values, and situation-specific skills in context. Therefore, **the evaluation framework takes the professional practice perspective into account** to view teacher-AI complementarity as a contextualised phenomenon and challenge shaped by and impacting the characteristics of the teacher.

In turn, D2.2 sets the foundation for **R2, the TAICo Knowledge Base**, by establishing the common evaluation structure through which empirical findings are generated, documented, and organised across the TAICo cases. Within the project, the knowledge base is defined as a structured collection of empirical results on the effects of AI integration on teachers’ profession, job, tasks, and skills. D2.2 supports this outcome by specifying the shared evaluation dimensions, procedures, and evidence categories that make case results sufficiently systematic for subsequent reporting, synthesis, and consolidation.

2. Conceptual foundations of the TAICo evaluation framework

Building on the initial TAICo framework presented in Figure 1, Figure 2 illustrates an evaluation logic in the form of the TAICo evaluation framework. While the initial TAICo framework defines the conceptual elements of teacher-AI complementarity and the socio-technical conditions that shape it, the evaluation framework translates these elements into a process-oriented structure for analysing how complementarity is shaped, enacted and evaluated across the TAICo cases.

Figure 2 TAICo Evaluation Framework

The evaluation logic links the **conditions** that make teacher-AI complementarity possible, the **enactment** of complementarity in a concrete interaction situation, and the **effects** that such complementarity can produce on teachers’ work and professional development in situated practice. A central idea of the TAICo evaluation framework is to assess these three contexts and their interconnections from two interrelated perspectives: human–computer interaction and professional pedagogical practice. From the human–computer interaction perspective, attention is given to how teachers interact with AI systems, including issues of usability, transparency, and levels of teacher-AI teaming (WP3). From the professional pedagogical practice perspective, the focus is on how these interactions are embedded in pedagogical activity, including teaching goals, instructional decisions, and the exercise of professional judgement (WP4).

In this sense, the TAIco evaluation framework also makes explicit how different TAIco workpackages (WPs) contribute to different parts of the evaluation logic. WP1 provides central methodological tools for modelling complementarity enacted in practice. WP3 contributes to the analysis of AI affordances, interface design principles, and teacher-AI teaming and its support. WP4 contributes to the analysis of teacher practice, professional development, and the role of design in professional development to support teachers' readiness.

The following subsections present in detail the structure and components of the TAIco evaluation framework. The role of the WPs and their research questions will be covered in Section 3. The precise operationalisation of the constructs and the collection of evidence will be introduced in Chapter 4.

2.1 Co-design as the entry point of the framework

In TAIco, teacher-AI complementarity is often shaped already in the early phases of design and implementation, where decisions are made about both the AI system and the pedagogical or professional practice in which it will be used. For this reason, co-design is treated as an important starting point that helps to explain the conditions under which later forms of complementarity may emerge.

Within TAIco, co-design takes place across three interrelated domains. First, **AI-interface co-design** focuses on the design of teacher-facing AI systems, including how system affordances, interaction options, transparency design features and teaming configurations are shaped to support teachers' professional practices. Second, **teaching practice co-design** focuses on pedagogical integration of AI tools into professional activities, including how AI-supported tasks are embedded into teachers' emerging or current professional routines. Third, the co-design of interventions for **teacher professional development (TPD)** focuses on the design of support structures and learning activities that help teachers understand, appropriately use and critically evaluate AI in their professional practice.

These co-design processes are important parts of the framework because they influence which forms of complementarity become possible, which forms of teacher agency are supported or inhibited, and how teachers experience AI. Co-design could act as a founding source of variation in how complementarity later develops across cases. Co-design is especially conducted in WP3 and WP4 through which guidelines for both technology design and professional development practices are produced by TAIco researchers along with stakeholders in teaching, teacher training, and the educational technology sector.

2.2 Layer 1: Complementarity conditions

The first layer of the framework focuses on the complementarity conditions: the set of pedagogical, contextual, institutional, and technological factors that make teacher-AI complementarity more or less likely to emerge in productive forms. Two types of conditions are treated as explanatory outcomes of the co-design phase and help explain why complementarity may take different forms across cases, tasks, and contexts.

The first condition type of this layer is the **teacher-AI teaming level**, which is dependent on the design principles of the AI systems that support teachers' actions for given pedagogical tasks. Different combinations of these variables could result in varying forms of teacher-AI interaction, ranging from low to high levels of teacher-AI co-adaptation and epistemic independence, including transactional, situational, operational, praxical, and synergistic levels (see [D3.1](#)). These forms do not act as fixed hierarchies, but as a useful way to differentiate between different interaction logics, distribution of responsibility, control and initiative between teacher and AI. For evaluation purposes, these configurations help distinguish whether AI supports only discrete functions, contributes to specific stages of a pedagogical task, or is integrated into a broader teacher-AI workflow, while the teacher retains responsibility for pedagogical judgment and decision-making. Teacher-AI teaming is largely dependent on certain capabilities of AI systems, including interface features that shape the interaction.

The second condition type of this layer focuses on the **professional practices** within which complementarity is situated. In TAIco, teacher-AI complementarity is studied in related (or near) professional and authentic practice cycles such as planning, application, and reflection of teaching practices (see [D4.1](#)), but also broader professional learning practices such as knowledge appropriation, maturation, and scaffolding. These practices matter because the same AI system may function differently depending on whether the tool is used for planning the learning process, assessment, feedback generation, adaptation of learning materials / tasks, or reflection and on how

meaningful the pedagogical integration of AI is. This refers to the alignment of the use of AI with professional principles of educational practice.

This layer also includes additional enabling or constraining conditions, described through **teacher background** variables (such as the teacher's prior knowledge and experience) and **different deployment conditions** (such as the professional support available, the broader institutional and organisational context, as well as technological deployment conditions). Those factors together may explain the structure of opportunities within which teacher-AI complementarity can emerge. Within the project, complementarity conditions are informed mainly by WP3, which examines AI design features, affordances, and teaming levels, and by WP4, which examines the role of professional development and co-design in shaping teachers' readiness and opportunities to work productively with AI. However, this layer also provides important context for interpreting later findings of the enactment and effects layers.

2.3 Layer 2: Complementarity enacted

The second layer, **complementarity enacted**, forms the analytical core of the TAIco evaluation framework. While the previous layer focuses on what makes complementarity possible, this layer focuses on what actually happens when teachers and AI work together on specific pedagogical tasks or within their practice. It is at this level that complementarity becomes observable and therefore empirically analysable.

In TAIco, enacted complementarity is mainly understood at two closely related domains: **task-level** and **skill-level complementarity**. Task-level complementarity is about how pedagogical tasks and subtasks are distributed between teacher and AI, including the sequence of actions, the division of labour, and shifting responsibilities across different parts of the task. Skill-level complementarity concerns how professional knowledge, reasoning, interpretation, and decision-making are implicated in the interaction: which capabilities remain mainly human, which are supported by AI, which are partially redistributed, and which may be strengthened or weakened through repeated use. Task-level and skill-level complementarity have direct implications regarding **task performance and cognitive load**. Research on human-AI complementarity typically focuses on task performance to determine whether the combination of human and AI performs at a higher level than either alone. In terms of teacher-AI complementarity, this might include task efficiency, the quality of outputs (lesson design, learning materials) and the quality of pedagogical reasoning and decision-making resulting from a task. At the same time, redistribution at the cognitive level may lead to either increased or decreased cognitive load for the teacher. While automation may reduce cognitive load, the introduction of AI tools, interfaces and data sources may also introduce additional processing demands.

The third domain in this layer concerns **teacher agency**, which can be observed within interaction. An important criterion for successful complementarity is that teachers retain control over critical pedagogical judgment and action. For this reason, the framework includes several dimensions of human agency, focusing on the enactment of agentic behaviour (which can be observed through self-regulation or other agency-related actions), the teachers' sense of agency during the interaction (sense of control, ownership, autonomy, and trust), and the degree to which shared agency is created in the interaction of human and AI. While AI can support teachers' work, it can also limit it, if it reduces teachers' interpretation, decision-making, or pedagogical reasoning. For this reason, enacted complementarity concerns not only how tasks are distributed between teacher and AI, but also whether the teacher retains meaningful agency in the interaction.

Taken together, an assessment of the redistribution of tasks and skills, along with an assessment of the teachers' agency in the process, can provide an indication of the **type of Teacher-AI complementarity** that is enacted in a particular situation, which describes the fourth domain in this layer as a form of interaction pattern. Initially, we describe this pattern as a **complementarity configuration** that integrates task-level, skill-level and agency-related findings into a characterisation of the kind of teacher-AI interaction occurring in each task episode. Drawing on the complementarity analysis introduced in D1.1, configurations are derived from patterns of action distribution, directionality of interaction, and skill and knowledge activation across the task sequence. Initial applications have identified structurally distinct patterns such as *decision-support complementarity*, in which AI generates data-informed suggestions while the teacher retains interpretive and decisional authority, and *prompt-based*

complementarity, in which the teacher's expertise shapes AI output through iterative dialogue. Further configurations are expected to emerge as additional TAICo cases are analysed.

Moreover, complementarity configurations can also be described in terms of the **enacted teacher-AI teaming** level (which may or may not have been enacted as expected, see Section 2.2). Although an AI tool's design establishes the *affordance* for particular forms of complementarity (i.e., teaming levels), the enacted configuration depends on how the teacher takes up those affordances in a specific task and context. The same tool can therefore give rise to different complementarity configurations and AI-teaming depending on teachers, tasks, and contexts. Furthermore, complementarity configurations can be described in terms of the **meaningfulness of the pedagogical alignment** that is enacted. For example, task-, skill and agency-related indicators may help explain whether the given interaction pattern is mainly operationally efficient or supports a more educationally meaningful form of collaboration that preserves human agency. For example, an AI-supported tool may reduce teachers' time or effort but, at the same time, narrow teachers' interpretation possibilities, weakening pedagogical control, or shifting attention away from student-centred reasoning. This may mean that more demanding interaction may at times be preferable if it supports teachers' reflection, professional judgement, and pedagogical quality of the work being supported. Similarly to the teaming levels, pedagogical meaningfulness will also depend on the contextual implementation and may differ from what had been intended (Section 2.2).

2.4 Layer 3: Complementarity effects

The third layer of the framework focuses on complementarity effects – the outcomes that follow from teacher-AI complementarity and interaction episodes. While during the interaction in a particular task more immediate effects can already be observed (such as task performance, cognitive load or the sense of agency that is experienced), this layer covers the broader developmental and professional effects of enacted complementarity episodes. This is important because a form of complementarity that appears useful in the short term may still be pedagogically limited or professionally problematic over time. For example, using AI, a teacher may be able to create more learning materials more efficiently and in a shorter time. However, not engaging deeply with some of the teaching materials may undermine the development of professional knowledge in that topic domain or with regards to a pedagogical approach.

Focusing on the wider professional consequences of (repeated) engagement in teacher-AI interactions, one important domain is **teacher professional knowledge and skills**. Depending on the case, this may include the development knowledge based on TPACK framework (Koehler & Mishra, 2009), AI literacy, pedagogical reasoning through situation-specific skills and metacognitive awareness.

A second domain concerns **teacher professional agency**. Here, the framework examines whether teacher-AI interactions and complementarity episodes support or constrain teachers' sense of themselves as capable, responsible, and professionally agentic actors. This goes beyond a particular task-level interaction (see Section 2.3) and instead adopts a broader professional and context-sensitive perspective on agency. Drawing on an ecological approach to teacher agency (Leijen, Pedaste, & Lepp, 2020), this perspective is not AI-specific, but it provides a useful conceptual basis for examining how AI-mediated practice may shape teachers' relationship to their work. From this perspective, agency may be examined across three interconnected dimensions. The **iterational dimension** concerns how prior experiences shape teachers' current capacity to act, for example, through self-efficacy grounded in earlier experiences with AI, digital tools, or teaching more broadly. The **practical-evaluative dimension** concerns situated professional judgement, including when, whether, and how AI tools should be used in pedagogically appropriate ways in specific teaching situations. The **projective dimension** concerns future-oriented confidence and orientation, such as willingness to adopt AI-supported practices, readiness to redesign teaching, and the ability to imagine new pedagogical possibilities.

A third domain focuses on AI-related **beliefs and attitudes**, including teachers' intentions to adopt AI-supported pedagogical practices, their perceived workload in relation to the AI use and their broader beliefs about the value and trustworthiness of AI tools in teaching and learning. Finally, job-level effects could also be included under this level. These involve changes in the demands of teacher work, such as perceived workload, wellbeing, cognitive burden or the redistribution of the effort across different task phases.

3. Research Focus of the Project

Section 3 describes the relationship between the TAICo evaluation framework and the research activities of WP1, WP3, and WP4, coordinated by WP2.

3.1 The Effects of AI on teaching tasks, skills and knowledge (WP1)

WP1 contributes to the TAICo evaluation framework by providing the analytical core for examining how pedagogical tasks and professional skills are reconfigured when AI is introduced into teaching practice. Its evaluation focus is centred on making complementarity empirically observable at the level at which it actually occurs: within actions, within tasks, and skill- and knowledge-demands that constitute a pedagogical task. The evaluation dimensions addressed by WP1 correspond mainly to the "complementarity enacted" layer of the framework (Section 2.3).

Across the three analysis levels (task-level, skill-level and complementarity), the three analytical components allow WP1 to address the overarching question of how the implementation of AI tools changes professional practices and what teachers need to know and be able to do within specific pedagogical tasks. Across the TAICo cases, WP1's analysis supports two closely related evaluation aims: first, to provide a granular empirical description of enacted complementarity that goes beyond broad characterisations of AI as "automating" or "augmenting" teacher work; and second, to generate evidence on skill and knowledge demands that can inform both AI design decisions (WP3) and professional learning trajectories (WP4).

Two overarching research questions guide WP1's contribution to the evaluation framework:

- RQ1.1: How does the implementation of AI tools into pedagogical practice change teacher tasks and the skills and knowledge required to perform them, and what effects do different AI design features, deployment conditions, professional development activities and teacher characteristics have on these changes (T1.4, T1.5)?
- RQ1.2: What configurations of teacher-AI complementarity emerge from these changes, and how do they vary across conditions and cases (T1.3)?

3.2 The role of AI tool design on complementarity (WP3)

WP3 contributes to the TAICo Evaluation Framework by examining how AI design and development features configure the interaction affordances through which teacher–AI complementarity is realised in practice. While design features refer to what teachers see and interact with, development features refer to the underlying mechanisms and technical capabilities supporting the system design. Building on the five levels of teacher-AI teaming (transactional, situational, operational, praxical, and synergistic) taxonomy presented in [D3.1](#), WP3 treats AIED systems not simply as technical artefacts, but as systems that enable (or constrain) particular forms of information exchange, control distribution, and co-adaptation between teachers and AI. These interactions are then analytically investigated as processes using complementarity analysis from WP1. Its evaluation focus is centred on understanding how AI design and development features influence not only task performance but also changes in teacher agency and professional competences in educational settings. In this sense, WP3 operationalises complementarity as a function of AIED system design. Design choices determine whether interactions remain at the level of request-response task execution (i.e., transactional teaming), progress towards bidirectional learning (i.e., praxical teaming), or higher-order cognitive exchange and co-reasoning (i.e., synergistic). Makes complementarity analytically traceable to design and development decisions. The evaluation dimensions addressed by WP3 span three interconnected layers of the framework: complementarity conditions (Section 2.2), complementarity enacted (Section 2.3), and complementarity effects (Section 2.4), reflecting its role in linking AI design and development features to both interaction processes and outcomes.

First, at the level of complementarity conditions, the framework should capture the design and development features of a teacher-facing AI system, including its AI characterisation and the level of teacher-AI teaming it supports. Drawing on the taxonomy developed in [D3.1](#), this dimension examines the technical characteristics of the AI system, the interface features through which it is accessed, and how these enable different forms of teacher-

AI interaction. WP3 captures how AI design and development features instantiate key interaction affordances, including shared state representations (situational teaming), goal specification and delegation mechanisms (operational teaming), iterative feedback and adaptation loops (praxical teaming), and capacities for negotiation, uncertainty handling, and epistemic challenge (synergistic teaming). These conditions are considered as configurations of AIED system design affordances that delimit the space of possible teacher-AI interactions. In this way, AI design is treated as a key explanatory condition that shapes the range and nature of possible interactions between teacher and AI.

Second, at the level of complementarity enacted, the framework should capture how these design and development features influence teacher agency within AI-supported interactions. This includes examining the extent to which teachers retain control over pedagogical judgement and decision-making, how they engage with AI-generated outputs, and how interaction design principles (e.g., representation sharing, uncertainty communication, initiative management, explanation for action, and co-adaptation) support or constrain their ability to exercise professional engagement. Here, WP3 focuses particularly on agency as it is enacted during task interaction, providing insight into how different interface and interaction designs shape teachers' sense of agency and judgements of agency in practice.

Third, at the level of complementarity effects, the framework should capture how variations in AI design and development features are associated with differences in task performance and professional outcomes. This includes examining immediate effects such as the quality and efficiency of task performance, as well as broader professional effects, including changes in teachers' skills, competences, and professional agency. In particular, WP3 considers how design and development features may support or constrain the development of situation-specific skills, pedagogical reasoning, and teachers' capacity to work productively with AI over time. These effects are not treated as independent of AIED system design, rather analyses them as emergent consequences of the underlying affordances including the extent to which systems support situational awareness, goal alignment, learning from interactions to adapt and epistemic exchanges between teachers and AI agents.

Together, these analytical components allow WP3 to reframe the evaluation problem from "what AI systems do" to "how AI system affordances structure teacher interaction" and "what are the implications of these interactions on educational practice and teacher competence". Across the TAICo cases, WP3 supports two closely related evaluation aims: first, to provide evidence linking AI design and development features to pedagogical and professional outcomes, teacher agency, and competence development; and second, to inform the design of human-centred, ethical teacher-facing AI systems that meaningfully support teachers' work, rather than simply automating pedagogical tasks. Three overarching research questions guide WP3's contribution to the evaluation framework:

- RQ3.1: What configurations of interaction affordances across teaming levels can foster teacher-AI shared agency?
- RQ3.2: How do different configurations of interaction affordances across teaming levels affect task performance within a given pedagogical task?
- RQ3.3: How do teachers perceive different configurations of interaction affordances across teaming levels within a given pedagogical task?

3.3 Evaluating professional learning and support for teacher-AI complementarity (WP4)

WP4 contributes to the TAICo Evaluation Framework by examining how professional learning, co-design and implementation support teachers in developing the knowledge, skills, dispositions, and practices needed for productive teacher-AI complementarity in teaching and learning processes. Its purpose is not only to assess professional learning activities as such, but to understand whether and how the professional learning approaches described in [D4.1](#) support teachers in working with AI in ways that are pedagogically meaningful, professionally sustainable, and developmentally valuable.

The evaluation dimensions addressed in WP4 correspond mainly to the complementarity effects layer of the framework, while also connecting to the conditions that enable enacted complementarity. Evidence in WP4 should address several interconnected dimensions. First, the framework should capture whether professional learning activities support **teachers' understanding** of the pedagogical purposes, affordances and limitations of AI tools in relation to specific pedagogical tasks, including evidence of changes in teachers' knowledge and their ability to

articulate when and why AI use is pedagogically appropriate. Second, the framework should capture whether **teachers develop situation-specific skills** relevant to teacher-AI complementarity (e.g., noticing relevant pedagogical situations, interpreting AI-supported outputs, making pedagogical decisions and adapting their practice in response to classroom activities). Third, the framework should examine whether **professional learning contributes to teachers' agency and readiness to work with AI tools**, including dimensions such as self-efficacy, trust in AI-supported outputs and willingness to adopt AI-supported practices. Fourth, the framework should examine whether **professional learning is associated with broader professional consequences**, such as changes in pedagogical reasoning, reflective practice, perceived role shifts, or emerging professional development needs.

These dimensions allow WP4 to understand whether professional learning in TAICo functions as a support structure for teacher-AI complementarity or more as an orientation to tool use. Across the TAICo cases, WP4 contributes evidence on how teachers develop the capacity to work productively with AI and how such development supports the enactment and teacher-AI complementarity in practice. Two overarching research questions guide WP4's contribution to the evaluation framework:

- RQ4.1: How do professional learning, co-design, and implementation support teachers in developing the knowledge, skills, and dispositions needed to work productively with AI in educational practice?
- RQ4.2: How does participation in professional learning influence teachers' enactment of teacher-AI complementarity and its professional and pedagogical effects?
- RQ4.3: How does AI integration affect the teaching profession, and what are the implications for future teacher roles, skills, and labour conditions?
- RQ4.4: How do teachers and school leaders perceive AI's impact on teaching roles and job quality?

4. Units of analysis, research methods and instruments

This section operationalises the evaluation framework introduced in Section 2 by specifying how its constructs are captured empirically across the diverse TAICo cases by specifying the units at which complementarity is captured (4.1), the categories of evidence the framework draws on (4.2), and the constructs through which evidence is interpreted (4.3).

4.1 Unit of analysis

Section 3 outlined the evaluation needs across WPs, and in this section, we now specify and describe how these dimensions can be captured empirically across TAICo cases. As the project includes diverse study designs, pedagogical tasks, AI systems, then TAICo evaluation framework provides a shared methodological structure that makes different forms of evidence comparable. We do it by specifying the unit of analysis and identifying the main source of evidence.

In line with the evaluation framework described in Section 3, we differentiate three different units of analysis when conducting research on teacher-AI complementarity:

- **Task episode:** The enactment of a particular Teacher-AI interaction embedded in an educational task and giving rise to a particular complementarity configuration. Each task episode can be described by its **conditions, structure and outcomes**
 - Conditions of the episode:
 - the intended AI-teaming level afforded by the tool
 - the intended alignment with pedagogical practice
 - the teachers and their background
 - Structure of the episode
 - Redistribution of tasks
 - Redistribution of skill and knowledge
 - Outcomes
 - increased or decreased task performance
 - increased or decreased teachers' cognitive load
 - enhancement or limiting of teacher agency

- observed alignment with meaningful pedagogical practice
- **Professional practice cycle:** A broader sequence of professional activity in which teacher-AI complementarity is embedded, and effects on practice can be observed. Each practice cycle can be described by
 - Conditions of the cycle
 - the AI tool and its deployment
 - the teachers and their background
 - Structure of cycle
 - Sequence of planning, implementation and reflection in teachers' teaching practice
 - Outcomes
 - Effects on professional knowledge, situation-specific skills and reasoning
 - Effects on professional agency, beliefs and attitudes
 - Effects on job and student outcomes
- **TAICo Case:** The broadest unit of analysis- a partner-specific empirical context in which one or more pedagogical tasks, AI tools, and studies are evaluated

All three units of analysis are nested, as the task episodes give rise to complementarity, the practice cycle situates those episodes within broader processes of professional learning and pedagogical adaptation, and the cases provide the level at which evidence is integrated and compared across the project.

4.2 Sources of evidence

Teacher-AI complementarity is not directly observable as a single variable. Our research instead needs to uncover the learning and thinking processes and span wide timescales (from the interaction in a task episode to change in practice to wider implications for the teaching profession). Our strategy, therefore, is to infer from patterns in teacher-AI interaction, the redistribution of tasks, changes in professional reasoning to the consequences these interactions have for teachers' work and development. For this reason, the TAICo Evaluation Framework relies on multiple sources of evidence that make different aspects of complementarity visible. Across cases, the specific methods and instruments may vary depending on the pedagogical task, the AI system, and the design of the study, but the framework distinguishes several broad categories of evidence that can be used in a comparable way in the project:

- **Expert-based judgements**- in some cases, evidence is generated through expert review of teacher-produced artefacts, coding of interaction quality, or expert assessment of pedagogical adequacy, teaming level, or task performance quality. Also, the analysis of task level, skill level changes and complementarity configurations is based on expert judgments. These approaches are needed when the aim is to evaluate dimensions such as the quality of AI-supported pedagogical outputs, the pedagogical appropriateness of teacher-AI interaction, or the extent to which a particular interaction reflects different levels or forms of complementarity.
- **Self-reported and elicited teacher perspectives** – sources may include surveys, short post-task ratings, interviews, and other forms of self-assessment, which are useful for capturing dimensions that are difficult to infer from observed behaviour, such as perceived agency, self-efficacy, trust in AI-supported outputs, perceived usefulness, workload, or intentions to adopt or adapt AI-supported practices. Also, broader job-level effects and student outcomes will not be observed directly but inferred from teacher reports or assessments. Self-report evidence is needed for the evaluation of professional and developmental dimensions of the framework, but within TAICo it is interpreted alongside behavioural and artefact-based evidence.
- **Observational and trace-based analysis** – includes classroom observations, screen recordings, interaction logs, logfile analysis, platform traces and the analysis of teacher-produced artefacts such as lesson plans, tasks, prompts, or AI-generated outputs that are selected, modified, or enacted by teachers. These sources are important for understanding enacted complementarity, because these approaches provide evidence of what teachers and AI systems actually do in relation to specific tasks and enable to

understand how tasks are redistributed, how information flows between teacher and AI, whether AI outputs are accepted or verified, and how teachers use or adapt AI-supported suggestions in practice.

- **Process-oriented elicitation methods** – aiming to make professional reasoning more visible: think-aloud protocols, stimulated recall, reflective tasks and other forms of structured reflection. Those methods are particularly valuable when the framework seeks to understand how teachers interpret AI-supported outputs, how they make pedagogical decisions, how they monitor or question AI contributions and for capturing situation-specific skills, pedagogical reasoning, metacognitive awareness, and the development of professional judgement in AI-supported practice.
- **Standardized or performance-based assessments** - knowledge tests, scenario-based or vignette-based tasks, standardized skill assessments, or structured evaluations of task performance. These sources are useful when the aim is to investigate how teachers develop forms of knowledge, reasoning, or situation-specific skills that are relevant to teacher–AI complementarity. Depending on the case, such assessments may be used to capture professional knowledge, pedagogical reasoning, AI-related decision-making, or the quality of AI-supported task performance.

These categories should be understood as complementary sources of evidence. In most TAICo cases, evaluation will rely on combinations of these sources and this is important because the framework is designed to capture both observable interactional patterns and less directly observable dimensions such as reasoning or agency. The next subsection therefore specifies the shared components through which these different forms of evidence can be interpreted in relation to the TAICo model.

4.3 Capturing main constructs across multiple sources of evidence

The constructs below operationalise the dimensions of complementarity identified in Section 2 and provide the shared analytical vocabulary through which evidence is interpreted across cases. Each construct is described along three dimensions: why it matters for understanding teacher–AI complementarity, how it is conceptualised within the framework, and how it can be measured given the diversity of TAICo case designs.

Task level changes

Why it is important: The introduction of AI into pedagogical practice rarely replaces whole tasks. More often, it reorganises the internal structure of a task, adding new actions, removing others, or redistributing responsibility for specific steps between teacher, tool, and AI. These changes are consequential because they shape what teachers do in the course of their work, what skills and knowledge they need to draw on, and where professional judgement is exercised. Without a structured account of task-level change, the effects of AI on teacher agency, workload, and professional practice are difficult to interpret, since there is no shared description of the work to which those effects attach. Task-level analysis therefore provides the foundational description of the episode on which other TAICo constructs depend.

How it is conceptualised: Task-level change is conceptualised as the difference between the baseline enactment of a pedagogical task (without AI, or with existing digital support) and its AI-supported enactment. Change is located at the level of subtasks and actions: which actions are *existing* (already part of the baseline task), which are *new* (introduced by AI support), and how responsibility for each action is distributed between teacher, AI, and where relevant, the user interface and the student. Task-level change also captures the *directionality* of teacher–AI interaction within actions, which determines whether the teacher leads, the AI leads, or the two iterate, and the *sequence* in which actions unfold. This conceptualisation follows the complementarity model developed in D1.1 and treats the task episode as the primary unit at which task-level change becomes observable.

How it is measured: Evidence in WP1 addresses several interconnected levels. First, the framework should capture **task-level change**: how the structure of pedagogical tasks is altered through the introduction of AI, including which subtasks and actions are added, removed, or redistributed between teacher, tool and AI, and how action sequences and directionality of information flows change. [Hierarchical Task Analysis \(HTA\)](#) provides the primary methodological tool for this, producing paired representations of baseline (before AI) and (several) AI-supported task configurations that make redistribution patterns visible and comparable across cases.

Skill level changes

Why it is important: The introduction of AI does not merely redistribute actions but reorganises cognitive work: some demands are reduced or externalised, while others, particularly those related to interpreting and evaluating become more salient. So, changes in pedagogical tasks become meaningful for professional practice when they are translated into the skills and knowledge teachers need to enact them. Skill level changes are consequential because they affect the nature of teacher expertise, cognitive load, the exercise of professional judgement, and the conditions under which teaching decisions are made. Without a structured account of skill-level change, it remains unclear whether AI introduces new skills and knowledge demands. Skill-level analysis, therefore, provides the necessary link between observable task changes and underlying cognitive processes within the TAICo framework.

How it is conceptualised: Skill-level change is conceptualised as the difference in cognitive, metacognitive, and knowledge-based demands between the baseline enactment of a pedagogical task and its AI-supported enactment. Building on task-level representations, each action is associated with the professional knowledge, situation-specific skills, and metacognitive processes required for its execution. Change occurs at the level of these demands and is described in terms of whether they are existing, changed, or newly introduced through AI support. This includes shifts in the type of knowledge required, the complexity and focus of situation-specific skills such as perceiving, interpreting, and decision-making, and the role of metacognitive processes. In line with the initial complementarity model in TAICo (D1.1), skill-level change reflects the distribution of cognition between the teacher and the AI. It specifies which cognitive processes remain under teacher control, which are supported or partially externalised, and which emerge specifically from interaction with AI. The task episode remains the primary unit of analysis, with skill-level change providing a second-order description of the cognitive demands embedded within it.

How it is measured: the framework captures **skill-level and knowledge change**: how cognition is distributed and how the cognitive and metacognitive demands placed on teachers shift due to task reconfiguration. Skill and Knowledge Analysis (SKA) provide a second methodological step to code the professional knowledge, situation-specific skills, and metacognitive skills involved in each action identified by HTA, and to identify which of these demands are existing, modified, or new.

Complementarity configuration

Why it is important: Task-level and skill-level changes describe how pedagogical tasks are reorganised, but they do not in themselves capture how teacher and AI operate together within pedagogical tasks and goals. Complementarity configurations address this by specifying the emergent patterns of interaction between teacher and AI that arise from these changes. These patterns are consequential because they shape where agency is located, how decisions are made, and how responsibility is distributed within AI-supported teaching.

Without an explicit account of complementarity, analyses remain fragmented: task-level descriptions indicate what is done, and skill-level descriptions indicate what is required, but neither explains how teacher and AI contributions are coordinated in practice. Complementarity configurations therefore provide an integrative layer that makes it possible to characterise different forms of teacher-AI interaction and to compare them across tasks, tools, and contexts within the TAICo framework.

How it is conceptualised: Complementarity configuration is conceptualised as the patterned alignment of task structures and skill distributions between teacher and AI within a pedagogical episode. It captures how responsibilities for actions and associated cognitive processes are jointly organised, and how interaction unfolds across the sequence of the task. Rather than treating complementarity as a fixed property of a tool or role, it is defined as a variable configuration that emerges from the interplay of task-level redistribution and skill-level change. This includes the directionality of interaction (e.g., teacher-led, AI-led, or iterative), the allocation of decisional authority, and the extent to which cognitive processes are internal, externalised, or co-constructed. Building on the complementarity model in TAICo (D1.1), configurations are understood as context-dependent patterns that can differ within and between tasks and teachers. The initial model remains open to the identification and refinement of additional configurations as further TAICo cases are analysed.

How it is measured: Third, the framework should capture **complementarity configurations** resulting from the HTA and SKA: the distinct patterns of how pedagogical actions, cognitive work, and decision-making are distributed between teacher and AI within a task episode. Complementarity is not treated as a monolithic property of an AI tool or a teaching role, but as a context-dependent configuration that may vary within and between pedagogical tasks and teachers. The complementarity analysis integrates HTA and SKA indicators to describe and characterise

these configurations, including where pedagogical framing, interpretation, monitoring, evaluation, and decision-making remain located, and how these are supported, externalised, or redistributed through AI-supported interaction. As additional TAICo cases are analysed, recurrent complementarity patterns may be identified and refined across contexts.

Task Performance

Why it is important: Task-level and skill-level analyses describe how teacher-AI work is reorganised, but they do not yet indicate whether the resulting pedagogical work is more or less successful. Task performance is therefore important because it captures both how efficiently teachers can carry out the pedagogical task and how good the resulting pedagogical output or decision is. In TAICo, task performance is a task-specific indicators of how well pedagogical work is carried out within a bounded episode.

How it is conceptualised: Task performance is conceptualised as the quality of teacher performance in relation to the main pedagogical task, including both process efficiency and quality of the resulting pedagogical outcome. Depending on the case, this may refer to how efficiently teachers complete a task, how much effort or iteration is required and whether the final output or decision is pedagogically strong. In TAICo, task performance is therefore understood as task-specific and context-dependent. It may include both process-level indicators (e.g., time, effort, fluency, number of revisions) and outcome-level indicators (e.g., quality of lesson design, appropriateness of feedback, accuracy of diagnostic interpretation) and should always be interpreted in relation to the pedagogical purpose of the task.

How it is measured: Task performance may be captured through multiple sources of evidence, depending on the case. **Efficiency-related indicators** may include task completion time, number of iterations, revisions or other trace-based indicators of how easily the task is carried out. **Outcome-quality indicators** may include expert ratings of teacher-produced artefacts (lesson plans, feedback messages, diagnostic decisions), coding of teacher responses in scenario- or vignette-based tasks, or task-specific indicators of decision quality.

Cognitive load

Why it is important: AI-supported work may reduce some forms of effort while at the same time introducing new cognitive demands related to monitoring, evaluating and adapting AI-generated outputs. Cognitive load is therefore important because it helps to differentiate AI support that productively reduces unnecessary burden and AI support that creates additional or poorly designed demands. The same teacher-AI configuration may appear efficient while still imposing substantial hidden demands on teachers' attention, interpretation or regulation. Cognitive load is therefore interpreted as an important experiential consequence of teacher-AI complementarity rather than as a standalone success indicator.

How it is conceptualised: Cognitive load is conceptualised as the mental effort associated with carrying out AI-supported pedagogical work. The specific conceptualisation depends on the study context, and the focus could be either perceived interaction burden, effort and frustration. In professional learning contexts the focus could be on task complexity, unnecessary burden introduced

How it is measured: Cognitive load is mostly captured through self-reported measures. Cases may use instruments such as NASA-TLX (Hart & Staveland, 1988), while training and professional studies in WP4 may use differentiated measures such as intrinsic, extraneous and germane cognitive load (e.g., Klepsch, Schmitz, & Seufert, 2017) or shorter indicators of active and passive load (Klepsch & Seufert, 2020). Where feasible, self-report may be complemented with process-based evidence such as repeated prompt reformulation, revision cycles, comparison across multiple sources of information, think aloud protocols that indicate where AI support reduces effort and where it introduces additional monitoring or interpretation demands. Those indicators could be treated as complementary proxies that strengthen the interpretation of self-reported data.

Workload

Why it is important: AI may reduce effort in some aspects of pedagogical work while at the same time creating new forms of hidden labour, such as prompt formulation, additional monitoring, verification of outputs. Workload is therefore important, because it captures whether teacher-AI complementarity really reduces burdensome work or merely redistributes effort in less visible ways. In TAICo, workload is especially relevant when evaluating whether AI support is professionally sustainable in real teaching practice (WP4)

How it is conceptualised: Workload is conceptualised as the perceived burden, effort and work intensity associated with AI-supported pedagogical practice and workload in TAICo refers more broadly to the practical and experiential burden of carrying out pedagogical work, including time pressure, task burden, monitoring effort and hidden

labour introduced by AI-mediated interaction. In longer-term implementation studies, workload may also be considered as part of teachers' evolving job-level experience

How it is measured: workload is usually captured through self-reported measures, implementation logs or reflection prompts that ask teachers whether AI-supported practices reduced, shifted or increased effort in meaningful ways. In some cases, workload may also be supported by trace-based or observational indicators, such as the number of revisions, repairs cycles, time spent verifying outputs or the extent of additional work required to make AI-generate suggestions pedagogically usable.

Teacher agency

Why it is important: Teacher agency is one of the central constructs in TAIco evaluation framework because an ethical approach to teacher-AI complementarity should ensure teachers retain meaningful influence over pedagogical decisions and action when interacting with AI-based systems. This is especially important in AI-supported teaching where AI systems first, provide static resources, but more importantly shape how information is presented, what options are foregrounded and how pedagogical choices are made. Across TAIco, the concept of agency helps distinguish between AI use that supports teachers' professional judgement and AI use that risks narrowing it. In contrast to more traditional educational tools, AI systems introduce an intelligible actor that actively participates in epistemic processes of knowledge creation, and the question of how agency is shared or distributed in this setting is of paramount importance. **How it is conceptualised:** In TAIco agency is conceptualised as the teacher's capacity to act intentionally and regulate their thinking, motivation, emotions and behaviour to reach goals. The project considers teacher agency in a broad sense, looking especially at epistemic agency, how it is shared between human and non-human actors, how it can be operationalized in concrete acts of regulation, and how this relates to agency in professional practice.

- **Epistemic agency** seems especially relevant as a concept when human AI-interaction is considered (Wu et al. 2025; Samuel, 2026). It refers to the capacity of individuals or groups to actively shape the knowledge and practices in a community (Scardamalia, 2002). It reflects the degree of autonomy and influence individuals or groups exert across the entire spectrum of knowledge creation (including goals, strategies, resources, and evaluation of results) (Scardamalia & Bereiter, 2006). This raises questions of how humans construct, evaluate, and take ownership of knowledge in environments where nonhuman systems now participate in meaning-making. **Shared epistemic agency** involves the intentional, collaborative effort of group members to create and advance shared knowledge objectives through coordinated knowledge-related and process-oriented actions (Damşa et al., 2010).
- Agency is exerted through purposeful **self-regulation** of thinking and acting which involves metacognitive processes such as planning, monitoring, evaluation and adaptation of cognitive strategies.
- **Professional Agency** considers teachers agency not in an AI-interaction task episode, but throughout a whole practice cycle, and from a broader ecological and professional learning perspective. The focus is whether professional learning strengthens teachers' capacity to work with AI while preserving professional judgement and supporting readiness for AI-supported teaching.

How it is measured: TAIco treats agency as a construct that can be captured through complementary forms of evidence: behavioral indicators of enacted control, self-report indicators of perceived control, and reflective accounts of professional judgement. Cross-case comparability does not require identical instruments, but it does require that the specific form of agency being examined is made explicit.

During task episodes (WP3, WP1):

- Distribution of control: HTA, SKA, and complementarity analysis can show where control is located in the task structure, whether teachers retain responsibility for interpretation and monitoring, and whether pedagogically consequential decisions remain teacher-led.
- Beliefs: Epistemic stance: Describes the epistemic beliefs that teachers bring into the interaction with AI (such as absolutist, multilist or evaluativist stance) (Wu et al. 2025)
- Actions: self-regulation actions (planning, monitoring, evaluation, adaptation)
- Sense of Agency (control, ownership, autonomy, trust): The focus is whether particular design or interface features support teachers' sense of control. This can be captured behaviorally through interaction traces, such as whether teachers accept, reject, modify, or override AI-supported outputs, and through self-report measures such as the Sense of Agency Scale (Tapal et al., 2017)

Focus on professional practice (WP4, WP1)

- Professional Agency (WP4): In addition to self-reported measures (e.g., adapted from Leijen et al., 2024), agency may be examined through teacher reflections or implementation logs that describe teachers' perceived room for decision-making, adaptation, and control in AI-mediated practice.

Trust

Why it is important: teacher AI-complementarity depends on how teachers regulate their resilience on AI-generated outputs. Too little trust may lead to underuse of potentially valuable support, while too much trust may lead to overreliance or bypassing of professional judgement and therefore, we see trust relevant as a condition for effective and responsible AI-supported practice.

How it is conceptualised: it is conceptualised as teachers' confidence in the usefulness, credibility and appropriateness of AI-supported outputs, as well as their willingness to rely on them in pedagogical work. Addition to our interest whether teachers trust AI, we are also interested in whether that trust is appropriate in relation to the quality, transparency and pedagogical reliability of the support provided.

How it is measured: trust may be captured through self-reported measures such as adapted trust-in-AI scales (e.g., Nazaretsky et al., 2022) as well as through behavioural indicators such as acceptance, rejection, override or repeated checking of AI-supported outputs. In some cases, think-aloud sessions or stimulated recalls may help to identify why teachers trusted, distrusted or selectively relied on AI suggestions.

Pedagogical meaningfulness of teacher-AI complementarity

Why it is important: In TAICo, efficient or even high-quality task-performance does not automatically mean that teacher-AI interaction is pedagogically meaningful. A teacher may complete a pedagogical task quickly, produce a strong immediate output, while still engaging only minimally in pedagogically meaningful work. For this reason, we also examine whether teacher-AI complementarity remains pedagogically meaningful and professionally desirable, meaning that task may appear effective at the level of task completion, while still narrowing teachers' pedagogical reasoning, weakening professional judgement or shifting responsibility away from the teacher in ways that are not educationally desirable

How it is conceptualised: Pedagogically meaningful and professionally desirable complementarity refers to whether a particular teacher-AI configuration supports pedagogical goals and preserves teachers' substantive role in pedagogical work. It is not treated as a fixed property of a tool or as a universal standard of 'good practice', but as an interpretive lens applied in relation to the pedagogical purpose of the case. In WP4, this lens is especially important for evaluating whether AI support teacher professional learning rather than improving only efficiency. Relevant criteria may include whether the interaction is based on a **clearly defined pedagogical problem**, learning goal, or instructional challenge; whether the **teacher remains actively engaged** in pedagogical work such as designing, monitoring, interpreting, adapting, or improving instruction; whether AI is used within an appropriate pedagogical role with **clear boundaries and retained teacher control** where needed; and whether the interaction supports rather than bypasses pedagogical reasoning, such as noticing, interpretation, decision-making, explanation, or justification.

How it is measured: pedagogical meaningfulness is not treated as a single measure, but as an interpretive judgement based on several sources of evidence. Relevant sources may include HTA, SKA and complementarity analysis to show who work and control are distributed, rating of pedagogical artefacts or decisions in relation to the case-specific pedagogical goal, think-aloud protocols, stimulated recall and so on that make visible whether teachers remain engaged in pedagogical reasoning. This helps to capture whether AI-supported interaction strengthens or weakens teachers' professional role over time and pedagogical meaningfulness is interpreted in relation to the broader pedagogical and professional value of interaction.

Professional knowledge

Why it is important: teacher-AI complementarity changes what kinds of professional knowledge is activated, relied upon, [developed](#) and potentially also ignored in pedagogical work. Professional knowledge is important, because it helps determine whether teachers are drawing on pedagogically grounded reasoning when working with AI-supported tools, or whether AI use risks substituting for knowledge that should remain the central to professional judgment. In TAICo, professional knowledge is especially relevant, because AI-supported interaction may amplify existing strengths in knowledge, but also expose gaps, or create new demands related to the interpretation of AI-generated outputs.

How it is conceptualised: Professional knowledge is conceptualised as the domain-specific, pedagogical, technological and AI-related knowledge that teachers draw on when engaging in AI-supported pedagogical tasks. Depending on the case, this may include knowledge about self-regulated learning or problem-solving, AI literacy, knowledge relevant to interpreting students' data or AI-generated suggestions. In TAIco, professional knowledge is examined both as a demand embedded into the task episodes (what knowledge is required or activated in given pedagogical task) and as an outcome in longer-term professional learning context (how teachers' knowledge changes across practice cycles)

How it is measured: professional knowledge is mainly captured through SKA as part of the analysis of the task episodes, where specific actions are linked to knowledge required to perform them (WP1). Knowledge can be also captured through self-reported instruments, knowledge tests, scenario- or vignette-based tasks, artefact analysis or reflections that reveal the knowledge that teachers draw on when designing, enacting or evaluating AI-supported practices (WP4). Cross-case analysis does not require identical knowledge instruments, but it does require that the knowledge domains relevant to each case are made explicit.

Situation-specific and metacognitive skills

Why it is important: Perception, interpretation and decision-making (PID) skills are important in TAIco, because teacher-AI complementarity in education depends on how tasks are distributed, also on teachers' ability to notice relevant pedagogical cues, interpret AI-supported outputs and make contextually appropriate decisions in teaching situations. In AI-supported teaching, these situation-specific skills are closely connected to metacognitive regulation, particularly when teachers need to monitor AI-generated suggestions, evaluate their pedagogical relevance and adapt their actions in response to classroom realities. While TAIco analysis can show where such demands arise within teacher-AI interaction, it is also important to understand whether teachers develop stronger situation-specific and metacognitive skills over time, which is especially relevant for WP4, where these skills may function as main professional learning outcomes of professional learning.

How it is conceptualised: We conceptualise those skills in two relate levels. At the episode level, they refer to the cognitive and metacognitive demands embedded in AI-supported pedagogical tasks, such as noticing relevant cues, interpreting AI-generated information, making pedagogically sound decisions and monitoring or adapting one's actions. At the professional learning level, they refer to teachers' evolving capacity to carry out these processes more effectively across tasks and over time. In this sense, the framework is interested in both- whether AI-supported tasks require teachers to notice, interpret, decide, monitor, or adapt, but also in whether repeated participation in AI-supported practice and professional learning strengthens these capacities in pedagogically meaningful ways.

How it is measured: In WP1, PID-related and metacognitive demands are addressed primarily through the analysis of enacted complementarity. HTA and SKA can help identify where within a pedagogical task teachers are required to interpret AI-supported information, monitor AI outputs, or make pedagogically **sound** decisions. In this way, WP1 helps make visible whether AI reduces, shifts, or increases the situation-specific and metacognitive demands placed on teachers within task episodes. However, these analyses do not directly measure skill development. In WP4, situation-specific and metacognitive skills are addressed from a developmental and professional learning perspective. The focus is whether professional learning supports teachers in developing the ability to interpret AI-supported outputs, make pedagogically grounded decisions, and reflect on the appropriateness of AI use in practice. These skills may be captured through performance-based and process-oriented approaches. In addition to reflections, relevant methods may include vignette-based tasks with varying levels of complexity, branching scenarios requiring sequential decision-making, analysis of teachers' responses to AI-generated artefacts, error-detection tasks in which teachers identify problematic AI-supported outputs, and stimulated recall based on interaction traces or screen recordings. Combinations of these approaches are especially useful because they can capture how teachers notice, interpret, monitor, and adapt under different levels of pedagogical complexity and uncertainty. In some TAIco cases, WP3 may also contribute indirectly by examining whether design features of AI systems support or constrain teachers' ability to notice relevant information, interpret AI suggestions, and remain actively involved in pedagogical decision-making.

Readiness for adoption

Why it is important: Even when an AI-supported interaction appears successful in a bounded task, this does not necessarily mean that teachers are willing or ready to adopt the practice in professional use. Readiness for

adoption is therefore important because it captures whether teachers see AI-supported practices as feasible, valuable, and professionally appropriate beyond the immediate task context.

How it is conceptualised: it is conceptualised as willingness and perceived feasibility to integrate AI-supported practices into their future teaching. It may include perceived usefulness, intentions to continue using the tools or practices and readiness to redesign teaching in response to AI-supported possibilities. In longer-term professional learning contexts, readiness for adoption may be interpreted as part of the projective dimension of professional agency.

How it is measured: Readiness for adoption is mostly captured through self-reported measures that address teachers' intentions (e.g. Ley et al, 2022), expected value and perceived cost based on expectancy-value theory (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020) and perceived barriers. In longer-term studies, it may also be examined through implementation evidence, such as reuse of AI-supported practices, continued engagement with the tool, or evidence that teachers adapt and AI-supported pedagogical routines over time.⁵ Case-level research plans for Phase II

5 Case-level Research for Phase II

While the previous sections set out the analytical and methodological structure of the evaluation framework, Section 5 presents how the framework is applied across the TAICo cases during Phase II. Section 5.1 maps the planned field studies and design implementation and evaluation studies onto the framework's evaluation logic. Section 5.2 summarises each case's research questions, designs, and methods. Section 5.3 describes how ethics, gender, and equality considerations are operationalised at the case level.

5.1 The planned studies for Phase II of the project

Figure 3 translates the evaluation framework (Figure 2) into a time-based view of planning the studies of phase II of the project. The two evaluation contexts, Interaction Analysis (green) and Impact Analysis (blue) are mapped to the timeframe of the field studies and evaluation studies of phase II. The purpose of the **field studies** is to evidence the effects of variations of complementarity conditions (e.g. varying the AI-teaming levels through preparation of two interface prototypes) on teacher-AI complementarity (e.g. the distribution on the task and skill levels) using quasi experimental research designs. The goal is to validate aspect of the model of teacher-AI complementarity proposed in D1.1.

The purpose of the **evaluation studies** is to evaluate particular design features of AI tools, deployment conditions or professional development interventions that have been co-designed in a participatory process with stakeholders. The goal is to contribute to validated guidelines for AI design and deployment in education and teacher professional development. While co-design of AI features and interfaces (WP3) will target the interaction layer of the evaluation framework (green), the co-design of PD interventions (WP4) will target the professional practice cycle (blue).

Figure 3: TAIco evaluation across field studies, co-design and evaluation studies

Due to different timescales and contextual conditions in the TAIco cases, the timelines and settings for empirical studies will differ. Also, how the different studies are linked is different across cases. The individual research plans for all TAIco cases will therefore be presented in the next section.

5.2 Research plans for Phase II of the project

In order to carry out evaluation of TAIco empirical results, this deliverable also outlines the planned research procedures in each TAIco case during the confirmatory research phase of TAIco. The table below summarizes the research questions and designs that each case plans to carry out in order to produce empirical results which drive the project results.

Table 1 Case-level research questions and research designs for confirmatory phase TAIco studies

Case	Research questions	Research design
Oulu	<p>Field study: How do interactions between students, AI, and the teacher differ in facilitating SSRL in collaborative learning when comparing groups supported by an AI agent which detects regulatory triggers to invite regulation as compared to groups supported by a simple AI system which invites regulation based on minimal cues of task structure?</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: What do teachers see as the affordances and trade-offs of the design of the metacognitive AI agent? What skills do teachers see as needed for facilitating SSRL supported by the metacognitive AI agent?</p>	<p>Field study: The study employs a comparative design in an authentic collaborative classroom setting involving 30 groups of Finnish middle school students (N = 30). Fifteen groups (n = 15) were supported by an AI agent capable of detecting regulatory triggers and adaptively inviting regulation, whereas fifteen groups (n = 15) used a simple AI system that invited regulation based on minimal cues of task structure. The AI supports the task of guiding collaborative learning through metacognitive trigger detection (rule-based, operational level).</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: Design-sprint workshop.</p>
UCL	<p>Field study: How do teachers perform/ behave differently in generating feedback for supporting collaborative learning classrooms with and without AI design features?</p>	<p>Field study: Real-world implementation comparing conditions with and without AI design features. The AI supports providing feedback for collaborative learning activities.</p>

	<p>Design implementation & evaluation: What are the impact of the proposed design features in teacher-facing AI tools that support feedback generation for HE CL context on teacher perceived agency and experience? How do the design features affect task performance? How do the design features affect teacher competence?</p>	<p>Design implementation & evaluation: Large-scale experimental control studies comparing different AI design features.</p>
UWK	<p>Field study: What impact does the (co-designed) AI tool have on practitioners learning design practices?</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: How do participants evaluate the AI-tool(s) in terms of perceived impact and usability?</p>	<p>Field study: Investigation of learning design practices (e.g., defining learning goals, selecting pedagogical approaches, authoring tasks) supported by AI chatbots.</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: Design-sprint workshop followed by evaluation embedded in field study.</p>
RUB	<p>Field study: How do dashboard aspects/capabilities of the tutoring system affect teacher actions and diagnostic skills? How do teacher characteristics and PD development affect the use of the dashboard and the tutor?</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: The design implementation will probably be part of the field study.</p>	<p>Field study: Experimental investigation of data-based decision-making using dashboard systems for monitoring and regulating individual student learning (rule-based).</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: Integrated within field study</p>
TLU	<p>Field study: How do variations in AI features and AI-enhanced practices affect teachers' pedagogical reasoning and sense of agency in authentic classrooms?</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: How does participation in the TAICo PD model support changes in situation-specific skills, pedagogical reasoning and how are these changes shaped by levels of AI support, individual teacher characteristics and contextual factors</p>	<p>Field study: Classroom-based implementation where teachers engage with AI-supported practices under varying levels of AI support (task: lesson design and pedagogical reasoning).</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: design-implementation-evaluation cycle to investigate how the professional training supports development of situation-specific skills, pedagogical reasoning, agency and practice over time.</p>
RU GenAI	<p>Field study: 1. How do teachers delegate the feedback interventions between themselves and the GenAI? 2. Under what conditions do secondary school teachers prefer a GenAI feedback assistant to act as advisory, co-decisional, or autonomous in project-based learning contexts?</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: 1. How do teachers perceive the GenAI tool based on their own lesson designs (in terms of usefulness)? 2. To what extent is the GenAI tool useful/usable? 3. To what extent would teachers adopt the AI-delivered feedback during their actual course design (and enactment)?</p>	<p>Field study: Investigation of teacher–AI interaction in feedback design for project-based learning (GenAI tool).</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: To be determined.</p>
RU Snappet	<p>Field study: Which subtasks (e.g., learning goal selection, progress analysis, grouping) do teachers use Copilot or Snappy (chatbot) for, and how does this differ between Copilot suggestions and Snappy use?</p>	<p>Field study: Longitudinal analysis of teacher–AI collaboration in curriculum adaptivity using the Snappet Copilot tool (focus on task delegation, interaction patterns, and teacher characteristics).</p>

	<p>How does the direction of information exchange (teacher initiated versus AI initiated) differ between Snappy and Copilot, and what type of cognitive function or skill do teachers delegate to Snappy?</p> <p>To what extent do teachers verify Copilot or Snappy output by looking up additional information in the dashboard, and how does this change over time?</p> <p>How do usage patterns and complementarity indicators change over time, and what role do teacher characteristics (e.g., AI literacy, self-efficacy, attitudes) play in these trajectories?</p> <p>How does prompt quality evolve over time, and how is it related to the quality of Snappy responses?</p> <p>How do differences in AI affordances and teaming levels (e.g., suggestion tool vs conversational agent; AI-initiated vs teacher-initiated support; degree of autonomy) shape (a) which subtasks teachers delegate, (b) interaction direction, and (c) verification behavior over time?</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: What impact does the AI tool have on teacher's lesson plan and curriculum design and how does it impact student learning/motivation/wellbeing?</p>	<p>Design implementation & evaluation: To be determined.</p>
--	---	---

These research designs are carried out using varied and context-specific methods tailored to the teachers and AI Ed systems that each case focuses on. As such, the following table outlines the methods planned for each confirmatory phase study across each case.

Table 2 Case-level methods for confirmatory phase TAICo studies

Case	Methods
Oulu	<p>Field study: Classroom video recordings of collaborative group work; interaction analysis conducted at the utterance level using structured coding procedures to compare interaction patterns across AI conditions.</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: Semi-structured interviews with teachers; qualitative analysis of teacher perceptions; descriptive quantitative summaries used where applicable.</p>
UCL	<p>Field study: Collection of teacher-generated feedback and AI-supported feedback interactions in small-group collaborative learning contexts; comparison across AI feature conditions.</p> <p>Design implementation & evaluation: Data from co-design workshops with teachers; pilot and large-scale evaluation data including teacher interaction with AI tools and feedback.</p>
UWK	<p>Field study: Observation and recording of teacher interactions with AI chatbot during learning design tasks; analysis of prompts and generated outputs.</p>

	Design implementation & evaluation: Data collected from co-design workshops and observational studies; analysis of teacher-generated learning designs and interaction processes with AI tools.
RUB	Field study: Collection of classroom dashboard data and teacher use of learner performance indicators; analysis of monitoring and regulation practices. Design implementation & evaluation: Analysis of teacher interaction; Data from co-design and observational studies inform baseline patterns of interactions, dashboard use and decision-making behaviors, providing insights into teachers' noticing. Data is used to inform the field study.
TLU	Field study: AI-supported lesson design and pedagogical reasoning tasks, interaction traces, AI-generated and teacher-adapted lesson artefacts, post-task vignettes for situation-specific skills and self-report measures of perceived agency and cognitive load. Design implementation & evaluation: Longitudinal collection of data across the professional training cycle, teacher reflections, implementation logs, and repeated performance-based assessments to capture changes in situation-specific skills, pedagogical reasoning, agency, and enacted practice over time.
RU	Field study: Collection of platform data across rollout phases, including student progress data and teacher use of AI-supported recommendations; within-person comparison (before vs after AI use). Design implementation & evaluation: Analysis of teacher interaction with chatbot (prompting, questioning, delegating tasks); collection of AI-generated lesson suggestions and usage data across phases.

5.3 Ethics, gender, and equality considerations

Phase II research treats ethics, gender, intersectionality, and equality as integral dimensions of the evaluation framework, in line with Task T2.2's commitment to ensure gender-sensitivity, inclusivity, and ethical integrity across all empirical activities. The project-level ethical framework- including governance structure, mitigation strategies, and monitoring procedures- is set out in D7.1 Ethics Plan and the [D6.2](#) Data Management Plan. This section focuses on how those project-level commitments are operationalised across the TAICo cases for Phase II.

Ethics approvals and governance

All Phase II studies are conducted under ethics approval from the relevant institutional review body, with no data collection beginning before approval is obtained. At the time of writing, approvals are in place for Oulu, RU, UCL, RUB, RU, and UWK; TLU's approval extension covering Phase II activities is in progress. Case-level ethics work is coordinated through the Implementation Task Force and the Ethics Advisory Board, which review study protocols, advise on critical cases, and support partners in resolving emerging issues.

Informed consent and data protection

Across cases, informed consent procedures follow a shared logic- written or digital consent in the official language of each country, in accessible terms, with clear opt-out and withdrawal rights- while accommodating local legal and institutional requirements. Studies involving minors (Oulu, RU, RUB) additionally obtain written parental or guardian consent.

Data protection arrangements follow the FAIR principles and the project's Data Management Plan. Participants are pseudonymised at the point of data collection, with identifiers stored separately from research data on encrypted, access-controlled institutional infrastructure. Sensitive data- audio, video, detailed interaction logs- receive additional technical and organisational safeguards.

Gender, intersectionality, and inclusivity

Approaches to gender and inclusivity vary across cases according to study design and the populations involved. Where feasible, partners aim for balanced gender representation at recruitment and report participant gender

transparently to support gender-disaggregated analysis (Oulu, RUB, TLU). UWK treats gender as a potential moderator. UCL does not record participant gender in its current design.

Inclusivity is addressed primarily through inclusive recruitment and accessible study design. For example, Oulu selected its partner school as representative of the local population and included an entire grade rather than a self-selecting subset; RUB notes that the software used in its case is suitable for students with dyscalculia; TLU aims to involve diverse participants where feasible and report relevant background characteristics transparently. The broader project-level commitments set out in the Project Description of the Action including the distinction between sex at birth and gender identity, attention to socioeconomic background, and gender sensitivity training for researchers- are coordinated at the project level through WP2 and the Ethics Advisory Board. Where individual case designs do not currently address all of these dimensions, this reflects the practical scope of each case. A distinctive design choice at Oulu is that the AI agent's voice is gender-ambiguous and matched to the local context in dialect and social class background, reducing the risk that voice characteristics introduce stereotype effects.

AI-specific considerations

Each case addresses bias, fairness, transparency, and accountability in ways that reflect the specific AI tool involved. The cases differ meaningfully in this respect: Oulu's tool is locally hosted and not used to train external models or make decisions about student outcomes; UCL primarily uses hypothetical scenarios with researcher and participant review of AI outputs where real data are involved; UWK relies on third-party generative AI services and explicitly addresses the resulting transparency limitations; RUB's software is rule-based, reducing concerns about non-transparent model behaviour; TLU explicitly considers bias, fairness, transparency, and accountability while ensuring teacher oversight remains central. In all cases, responsibility for evaluating and validating AI outputs rests with the research team. The systematic AI-tool register, audit procedures, and information sheets that underpin these decisions are documented in D7.1.

Risks and mitigation

Most cases share a common risk profile: time burden, possible discomfort with audio or video recording, and concerns about performance evaluation.

Oulu additionally identifies the risk of teachers or students over- or under-relying on the AI system for learning regulation. Mitigation strategies are common across cases- voluntary participation, the right to withdraw without consequence, confidential data handling, and an explicit commitment that data are not used for performance evaluation. Oulu additionally instructs teachers to continue supporting students directly if AI support appears ineffective, ensuring that the study itself does not displace pedagogical judgement during the activity.

6. Conclusions and future outlook: evaluation of TAIco results to form a Knowledge Base

This concluding section reflects on what D2.2 has delivered and looks ahead to how the evaluation framework will support the next phase of TAIco's empirical work. The framework set out in this deliverable provides the methodological base for the case-level studies described in Section 5; the cross-case synthesis these studies will produce, in turn, will contribute to the project's subsequent deliverables — the intermediate report of TAIco cases (D2.3), the synthesised case reports (D2.4), and ultimately the TAIco Knowledge Base (D2.5).

This holistic view of the research conducted across all cases and partners is what enables the TAIco Knowledge Base - a project-level result synthesising all empirical results of the project, and it will inform diverse stakeholders - from AIEd researchers and developers, to teachers and teacher educators, to EU policymakers and research funding bodies. For this reason, it is crucial that research carried out in TAIco takes the broad sociotechnical conception of the project's research, with perspectives from both human-computer interaction and from teacher professional practice, into account.

To move toward the Knowledge Base synthesizing TAICo results across the project, comparing TAICo results at the level of the cross-focal concepts ensures that the TAICo Knowledge Base is communicated coherently across the different study types and contexts of the TAICo cases. Phase II studies across TAICo cases will therefore consider their results through the conceptual lenses and candidate instruments enumerated in this framework, **enabling both construct-level and instrument-level cross-case comparisons**. In establishing this evaluation framework, we have begun collation of a TAICo Instruments and Codebook internal document by which partners can share instruments and methods used for analysing each construct, reuse instruments across cases, and align on terminology and analysis techniques within and across cases.

7. References

Amershi, S., Weld, D., Vorvoreanu, M., Fourney, A., Nushi, B., Collisson, P., ... & Horvitz, E. (2019). Guidelines for human-AI interaction. In *Proceedings of the 2019 chi conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1-13).

Blömeke, S., Gustafsson, J. E., & Shavelson, R. J. (2015). Beyond dichotomies. *Zeitschrift für Psychologie*.

Eccles, J. S. & Wigfield, A. (2020). From expectancy-value theory to situated expectancy-value theory: A developmental, social cognitive, and sociocultural perspective on motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101859>

Gao, Q., Xu, W., Pan, H., Shen, M., & Gao, Z. (2025). Human-Centred Human-AI Collaboration (HCHAC). In *Handbook of Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence*.

Hart, S. G., & Staveland, L. E. (1988). Development of NASA-TLX (Task Load Index): Results of empirical and theoretical research. In *Advances in psychology* (Vol. 52, pp. 139-183). North-holland.

Ritzmann, S., Hagemann, V., & Kluge, A. (2014). The Training Evaluation Inventory (TEI)-evaluation of training design and measurement of training outcomes for predicting training success. *Vocations and Learning*, 7(1), 41-73.

Samuel, A. (2026). Learning with Machines: Toward a Theory of Epistemic Co-Agency. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 100573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CAEAI.2026.100573>

Song, B., Zhu, Q., & Luo, J. (2024). Human-AI collaboration by design. *Proceedings of the Design Society*, 4, 2247–2256.

Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view1. *MIS quarterly*, 27(3), 425-478.

Wu, J. Y., Lee, Y. H., Chai, C. S., & Tsai, C. C. (2025). Strengthening Human Epistemic Agency in the Symbiotic Learning Partnership With Generative Artificial Intelligence. *Educational Researcher*, 54(6), 358–368. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X251333628>

Zhang, S., Wang, H., & Yi, X. (2025). Exploring Collaboration Patterns and Strategies in Human-AI Co-creation through the Lens of Agency: A Scoping Review of the Top-tier HCI Literature. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 9(7), 1–43.

Taico

Teacher-AI Complementarity

www.taico-project.eu

@Taico_project

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Project Number: 101177268